

OBSERVATION OF STOCHASTIC DAMAGE IN MICROCOMPOSITE MONOLAYERS UNDER TENSILE STRESS BY VIDEO MICROPHOTOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Recent results on the mechanical behavior of single para-aramid and carbon fibers are presented. The effects of fiber length and diameter variabilities on strength are obtained for the para-aramid fibers, and the effect of strain rate on strength is obtained for carbon fibers. The data are analyzed by using the common two-parameter Weibull failure distribution. We present results from failure tests conducted with microcomposite monolayers made of single fibers (of various types) carefully disposed in a thermosetting resin. The monolayers were tested for strength using a custom-made minitensile testing apparatus fitted to the stage of a stereozoom microscope, and damage nucleation and growth was followed by video microphotographic means. The potential usefulness of microcomposite monolayers in the characterisation of basic failure modes of fibre-reinforced composites, and of the dynamics of failure in such materials, is demonstrated. The video microphotographic observation of the failure process in composite materials may also be used as a probing tool for some of the basic hypotheses in current probabilistic theories of composite strength.

INTRODUCTION

The elementary failure modes in unidirectional composites are still not well understood and are currently subjects of renewed interest. The approach taken here to study this problem is to attempt linking the mechanical response of the larger composite structure with the behavior and structure of the single fiber. We show first that simple statistical concepts, based on modifications of the Poisson/Weibull approach resulting in a new failure probability function, can be used satisfactorily for the study of size effects on strength in para-aramid fibers. Next, the effect of strain rate on the strength of carbon fibers is examined for three types of carbon fibers. Finally, a new experimental approach for the study of composite failure is presented, consisting of specially prepared composite monolayer models tested in simple tension under an optical microscope equipped with crossed polarizers and with a video camera. The potential usefulness of this approach for the characterisation of basic failure modes in fibre-reinforced composites, and as a probe of existing strength theories in such materials, is demonstrated.

EFFECT OF LENGTH AND DIAMETER ON FIBER STRENGTH

The theoretical basis for the effect of fiber diameter variability upon strength is usually provided through a relationship of the form ^{1,2}:

$$1/\sigma \sim D^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the strength and D is the fiber diameter. This is a Griffith-like expression but in which the fiber diameter rather than the critical crack length is used. Statistical theories, generally

based upon the Weibull probability distribution combined with the weakest link concept, describe length effect via the expression ³:

$$\bar{\sigma}(l) \sim l^{-1/b} \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ is the mean strength at a given (nondimensional) length l , and b is the shape parameter in the two-parameter Weibull probability distribution for strength. One way to take fiber to fiber diameter variability into account is to use the following failure distribution function ⁴:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\{-kd^{\delta}\sigma^b\} \quad (3)$$

where $F(\sigma)$ is the probability of failure of a fiber under a stress σ or less, d is the (nondimensional) fiber diameter, k is a positive constant, and δ is a real constant. With the failure distribution function given by equation 3, termed here the modified Poisson/Weibull distribution, size effects are described by the expression:

$$\bar{\sigma}(l, d) \sim l^{-1/b} d^{-\delta/b} \quad (4)$$

and the slope of a $\ln(\bar{\sigma})$ vs. $\ln(d)$ plot is equal to $-\delta/b$. As seen, the shape parameter is not anymore the only parameter determining the size effect as in previous statistical model: rather, $-\delta/b$ is now the determining factor. At the condition that δ takes on the appropriate numerical value, the values of b obtained from a modified Weibull plot -through linearization of equation 3- and from the $\ln(\text{strength})$ vs. $\ln(\text{diameter})$ plot are reconciled. Recent experimental work ⁴⁻⁷ amply justifies the use of a modified Poisson/Weibull scheme (equation 3) to account for size effects in fibers. As an example, Kevlar 149 para-aramid fibers were used ^{6, 7} and shown to fit better equation 3 than a conventional Weibull model. Moreover, the modified Poisson/Weibull approach was shown to fit a $\ln(\text{strength})$ vs. $\ln(\text{diameter})$ plot in a way at least as satisfactory as a linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM)-like model (equation 1). Finally, the modified statistical model reconciled the values of the shape parameter b as calculated from a Weibull plot and a $\ln(\text{strength})$ vs. $\ln(\text{diameter})$ plot (see references 6 and 7). Various other examples are available in the above cited references.

EFFECT OF STRAIN RATE ON FIBER STRENGTH

The statistical/probabilistic approach may be used to model strain rate effects on strength in polymeric fibers through the dependence ⁸:

$$\sigma(\dot{\epsilon}) \sim \dot{\epsilon}^{1/(\rho+1)} \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, and ρ is a numerical constant which, from lifetime experiments under constant loading (which involve ρ as well), was found ⁸ to be of the order of 45 for Kevlar 49. Equation 5 predicts a slight increase of strength against strain rate in log-log coordinates. The strain rate dependence of strength has also been studied by Lhymn et al. ⁹.

Low-, medium-, and high-modulus pitch-based carbon fibers produced by du Pont were tested for strength in our laboratories and shown to fit satisfactorily a two-parameter Weibull distribution at eight different strain rates (ranging from 0.00004 to 0.02 sec⁻¹). The fiber length used was 21 mm. The modulus range was between 250 and 750 GPa. The structural differences among the fibers were apparent in their strain rate dependence, as demonstrated in figures 1 and 2 in which the

Weibull shape and scale parameters (calculated by maximum likelihood estimation⁴) are plotted against the rate of strain. Each point reported corresponds to a result over a set of 30 samples. In figure 1 the shape parameter is seen to increase rapidly with the rate of strain at low rates, for the three types of carbon fibers tested. After a maximum is reached, a progressive, slow decrease with strain rate is observed. The scale parameter exhibits a decrease of the scale parameter with strain rate for LM and MM carbon fibers, which is preceded by an increase up to a maximum for the HM carbon fiber. In figure 2 we have plotted the scale parameter against strain rate in log-log coordinates so that we can compare the results with the prediction of equation 5. For comparison we also report in figure 2 the results of Schwartz et al.¹⁰ for ultra-high strength polyethylene (spectra 900) fibers. The value of ρ is unknown for carbon so we have used $\rho \approx 45$. As seen spectra 900 shows an increase of strength with strain rate (which is perhaps larger than predicted by eq. 5 but ρ may be different from 45 in polyethylene). The carbon fibers show a more complex behavior particularly at high strain rates where a sharp decrease of strength is clearly present. In polymeric fibers such as spectra 900 it is generally accepted that the fracture process is dominated by viscoelastic effects¹¹. This argument however is not applicable to carbon fibers which fail in a brittle way. Lhymn et al.⁹ report a trend for the strength against strain rate in carbon fiber mat/cement composites which is similar to the trend observed here in single carbon fibers. A tentative, approximate explanation for the strength-strain rate behavior observed in carbon fibers is as follows. It may be that at high rates of strain the worst flaw dictates a weakest link type of behavior especially in the HM fiber which possesses higher strength variability (uneven flaw distribution, see the lower shape parameter). At lower rates, however, a larger number of flaws, of various sizes, may develop up to a critical size (damage accumulation), a process which might induce higher strength values. More work on this is currently underway.

DAMAGE ANALYSIS IN COMPOSITE MONOLAYERS

An accepted approach to the problem of fracture nucleation in unidirectional composites is to view it as a complex statistical/stochastic process involving scattered failure of fibers at flaw sites, and local overloading and failure of neighbouring fibers by way of stress transfer through the matrix. It is also commonly predicted, via several variants of a model for crack growth, that final (catastrophic) failure follows via the rapid development of a cluster of neighbouring broken fibers, possessing a critical dimension. Composite **monolayer models**, which consist of carefully positioned single fibers into a thin epoxy matrix layer, were fabricated using a specially developed technique. Details of the manufacturing method are given elsewhere^{12, 13}. The monolayers, of various types, were tested to failure in simple tension using a custom-made minitensile testing device fitted to the stage of a stereozoom microscope. The fracture nucleation and growth process was followed by video microphotography. The experimental setup is sketched in figure 3. The fiber used were E-glass (Vetrotex), Kevlar 29, Kevlar 49, and Kevlar 149 (du Pont). The matrix system was CY223/HY956 epoxy (Ciba Geigy). Complete details of the results regarding our preliminary tests are given elsewhere¹³. As an example the modulus of Kevlar 149/epoxy monolayers made of 1 single fiber, and of 8 single fibers, was found to follow quite well the Halpin-Tsai (or rule-of-mixtures, RoM) equation, even at very low volume fraction. Also, the strength (shown in figure 4) was found to increase linearly according to the RoM. These results, although preliminary, are encouraging and confirm that the quality of the manufactured microcomposites is high. The study of microcomposites via videomicrophotographic techniques is particularly relevant to the dynamics of mechanical fracture in such materials. Indeed, with respect to failure dynamics, the first findings of our research are as follows:

(i) As predicted by several authors (see reference 13) a critical number of neighbouring fibres must break before fast failure occurs. Based on a very limited number of preliminary tests, this number was found to be equal to 4 in E-glass/epoxy microcomposites. In Kevlar 149/epoxy

microcomposites, the crack growth process is extremely fast, but some fibre integrity is conserved (fibre splitting rather than snapping occurs).

(ii) In principle information on the type of load sharing rule in effect in a given fibre/matrix system can be obtained. A fast-propagating damage array is observed to nucleate and grow in Kevlar 149/epoxy systems, at several places simultaneously. This may indicate that equal-load sharing is in effect in this system.

(iii) In principle, the effect of changes in the chemical or physical nature of interfaces on the failure nucleation, growth, and criticality can be studied. This is currently pursued.

(iv) The effect of fibre bunching (that is, the fibre-to-fibre interaction) and/or of volume fraction, as well as of fibre misalignment, on the mechanical and fracture properties can easily be assessed. This is also currently being studied.

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Fig. 1 - Weibull shape parameter against strain rate in low-, medium-, and high-modulus carbon fibers.

Fig. 2 - Weibull scale parameter against strain rate (in log-log coordinates) in low-, medium-, and high-modulus carbon fibers. For comparison we have included spectra 900 data from Reference 10 as well as equation 5 in this work.

Fig. 3 - The experimental setup, including a PS/2 microcomputer and a video graphic printer currently added.

Fig. 4 - Tensile strength against fiber content in Kevlar 149/epoxy microcomposite monolayers.